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P2-162 A Meta-analysis of Worldwide Mycotoxin Prevalence in Beers

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Introduction: Beer is the second most popular alcoholic beverage consumed in the world. Mycotoxins have been reported to occur in beers around the world.

Purpose: The purpose of this research was to estimate the worldwide prevalence of mycotoxins in beers through a systematic review and meta-analytic approach for incorporation into quantitative risk assessment.

Methods: Citations related to mycotoxin occurrence in beer from 1986 to 2018 were retrieved from Web of Science, Scopus and PubMed. The prevalence of mycotoxins in beers by WHO region and country was subjected to meta-analysis. Data on total aflatoxins (AF), AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁ and AFG₂; deoxynivalenol, 3- and 5A deoxynivalenol (DON); total fumonisins, FB₁, FB₂, FB₃, (FBs); ochratoxin A (OTA); T-2 and HT-2 toxin (T2t); zearalenone (ZEA) and “other mycotoxins” was extracted from collected citations. Regression was performed to assess correlation between mycotoxin prevalence and year of publication. Logit transformation was applied to normalize the data and random-effects were estimated by maximum likelihood. Heterogeneity was calculated via the I² statistics test. Data analysis was performed using Metafor and Meta packages in R Statistical Software using $P < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 73 articles with 4970 samples from among 5219 potential articles were included in the meta-analysis and meta-regression. The global pooled prevalence of mycotoxins in beers was 17% (95% CI=14-22%), with substantial heterogeneity (I²=96.55%, $P < 0.0001$). The overall rank order of prevalence was OTA>FBs>DON>other mycotoxins>ZEA>AFs>T2t. The regions with highest and lowest reported beer mycotoxin prevalence were Africa (24%) and Eastern Mediterranean (4%), respectively. Countries with highest and lowest prevalence were Iran (99%) and China (1%), respectively. Meta-regression showed a significant decrease in the prevalence of mycotoxins in beers over time (C=-0.0094; $P < 0.05$).

Significance: Data showed substantial heterogeneity in the occurrence of mycotoxins in beer and suggest further actions to reduce the risk of exposure may be needed.

P2-163 A Meta-Regression Model Describing the Effects of Essential Oils on *Escherichia coli* Inactivation in Cheese

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Introduction: The antimicrobial properties of plant essential oils have been described in the literature and proposed as hurdles to increase the microbiological safety of many food products, including cheese.

Purpose: The objective of this study was to integrate data on *Escherichia coli* (EC) inactivation in cheese containing essential oils (EOs) by means of an overarching meta-regression model.

Methods: Suitable primary studies were identified through exhaustive literature search. Sixteen studies were considered appropriate for inclusion ($N = 362$), and the following study characteristics were extracted: antimicrobial, mean log reduction, storage temperature, exposure time, antimicrobial application (i.e., cheese mixture, cheese surface, milk, or film), and antimicrobial and pathogen's inoculum concentrations. Studies were assigned weights according to the sample size (n) used along the experiment while the different antimicrobials were assumed to cause shifts as random effects. The significance of moderators was evaluated by analysis of variance ($\alpha=0.05$).

Results: The meta-regression revealed the significant impact of application type ($P < .0001$) and antimicrobial concentration ($P = 0.002$) on EC log reduction. Exposure time was also found to affect EC inactivation, although such effect is dependent on the type of application ($P < .0001$). This means that, for a specific antimicrobial, the same inhibitory effect is achieved with distinct exposure times, depending on the application type selected. Milk was found to be the application mode leading to highest microbial reduction, while incorporation in cheese mixture, cheese surface and films presented lower inhibitory effects. Among the types of EOs meta-analyzed, shallot, sage and lemon balm produced the greatest mean bactericidal effects. Heterogeneity analysis revealed that the moderators explain >95% of the between-antimicrobial variability.

Significance: This meta-regression model offers insight on the main causes of variability in microbial reduction, which can be useful for the experimental design of challenge studies and for the optimization of the use of essential oils as a biopreservation technology for pathogen control in foods.

P2-164 Inactivation of Antimicrobial Resistant Bacteria during Manure Storage as Static Stockpiles

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Introduction: Humans may be exposed to antimicrobial resistant bacteria (ARB) with an origin of food animal husbandry through environmental routes due to the contamination from livestock manure. Appropriate treatment and management of manure is critical to mitigating ARB spreading to the environment.

Purpose: Quantitatively evaluate the survival of tetracycline resistant (TETR) *E. coli* during manure storage as static stockpiles and estimate storage time sufficient to inactivate TETR *E. coli* below the limit of detection (LOD) or quantification (LOQ).

Methods: Manure samples were collected from various depths (core, mid, and surface) of three manure stockpiles at 9 sampling occasions over a three-month period. The presence and load of TETR *E. coli* along with moisture content for each sample were measured. The survival curve of ARB was described by fitting several generalized linear mixed models (Gamma, Exponential, and Weibull) with and without the covariate effect, i.e., moisture content. The upper bound of 95% confidence interval was used to conservatively estimate the time required to inactivate TETR *E. coli* below LOD or LOQ.

Results: The response denoting loads of TETR *E. coli* in log CFU/g showed a positively skewed distribution. Weibull distribution had the smallest mean square prediction error (MSPE) and was the best fit for modeling the response variable with random effects due to pens, depths, and sampling days. Overall, 48 days were required for TETR *E. coli* to reach the LOQ (2.30 log CFU/g) and 170 days to reach the LOD (-1.00 log CFU/g).

Significance: These findings provide a science-based evidence informing appropriate manure management practice and may contribute to combating antimicrobial resistance.